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Servant Leadership, Innovativeness, and Servant Performance

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Abstract

This study aims to examine and analyzes the effect of servant leadership on servant performance and innovativeness. Besides, the impact of servant leadership on innovativeness is also checked and analyzed. Moreover, to attain this goal, this study applies the servants from one of the churches in Bandung: *Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud*, as a population. Based on the calculation of Issac dan Michael's formula, the samples needed are 164. However, after data collection by survey in November 2021, the responded servants were 90. Therefore, the response rate is 71.43%. This study utilizes a structural equation model based on a partial least square by considering the total samples below 100. After testing the data, this study concludes that servant leadership positively affects servant performance and innovativeness. Also, this positive sign is obtained in the association between servant leadership and innovativeness.

Keywords: Innovativeness, Servant Leadership, Servant Performance

1. Introduction

The church is the body of Christ (Barth, 1958). Furthermore, God sets the people to be apostles, prophets, and teachers to serve the congregations as the body (I Corinthians 12:28, KJV). Indeed, to execute it well, they are equipped with specific gifts from Holy Spirit: speaking with wisdom and knowledge, getting faith, performing healing, miracles, and prophecy, discriminating various spirits, and speaking and translating the tongues (I Corinthians 12: 8-10, KJV). According to Ngatang (2010), wisdom becomes a tool for leaders to create proper leadership.

Related to this issue, what is leadership style suitable for the congregation? The biblical papers recommend that servant leadership be precise for the church (Flanike, 2006; Machokoto, 2019; Lewis, 2019; Du Plessis & Nkambule, 2020; Kambey, 2022). It happens because Jesus Christ teaches His disciples to be servants (see Matthew 20:26-28 and Luke 22:27, KJV). Besides, He proves what He teaches by cleaning the foot of His disciples (see John 13:14, KJV). Also, Paul in Philippians 2:7 (KJV) affirms what Jesus takes place in His incarnation as

the man as the servant. Furthermore, this leadership will direct the congregations' lifetime toward Jesus Christ (Fransisca & Laukapitang, 2020) through faith-building through Biblical study (Hill, 2014).

During the Covid-19 pandemic, churches need innovation, especially in worship, teaching, evangelism, service, and fellowship (Covarrubias et al., 2021). Because of the social distance to prevent coronavirus infection, these activities are no longer conducted on-site but virtually (Mahiya & Murisi, 2022). Furthermore, churches use live streaming media to facilitate worship, such as YouTube, which everyone can access (Kgatle, 2020), and online platform meetings, like Zoom, to make fellowship (Mahiya & Murisi, 2022), which their invited members can join (Addo, 2021).

The papers focusing on servant leadership in the church are numerous. Unfortunately, they are conceptual and do not statistically examine the relationship between servant leadership and performance (Flanike, 2006; Machokoto, 2019; Lewis, 2019; Du Plessis & Nkambule, 2020). The papers with employees from non-organizational churches dominate this research: faculty members (Saleem et al., 2020), employees working in the third sectoral entity (Hernández-Perlines & Andrés Araya-Castillo, 2020), forest department (Tripathi et al., 2021), university (Sarwar et al. 2022).

Related to innovation, the study of Parulian S. et al.(2021) only describes the survey outcome about leadership in the church. Unfortunately, it does not statistically associate innovation with servant leadership and performance. Also, the existing papers investigating the relationship between servant leadership and innovation still utilize the employees working in a manufacturing company (Opoku et al., 2019), the third sectoral entity (Hernández-Perlines & Andrés Araya-Castillo, 2020), firms in the sector of information technology and communication (Iqbal et al., 2020; Bou Reslan et al., 2021). Besides, the manuscripts investigating the association between innovation and performance take the employees working in small-medium firms (Saunila, 2017) and the third sectoral entity (Hernández-Perlines & Andrés Araya-Castillo, 2020).

Regarding these gaps, this study wants to enrich theological research literature with the quantitative method through hypothesis development by surveying the servants of congregations in *Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud*, Bandung. Furthermore, the servants intended are under the board of elders as the top leader in the organizational structure.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. *Servant leadership and performance*

In their study, Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020) demonstrate a positive association between servant leadership and the performance of the employee working in the third sectoral entity. Employing employees in the Forest Department of Uttar Pradesh, Tripathi et al. (2021) confirm this positive tendency. Sarwar et al. (2022) also confirmed this positive sign when inspecting the impact of love, altruism, trust, and service as four dimensions of servant leadership on the enactment of employees from the University of Sargodha. However, empowerment as another dimension of servant leadership does not affect this performance. Besides, by utilizing faculty members in Pakistan as the samples, Saleem et al. (2020) prove a positive tendency of servant leadership on subordinates' job performance. By denoting this evidence, this study offers the first hypothesis as follows.

H₁: Servant leadership positively affects servant performance

2.2. *Servant leadership and innovativeness*

With servant leadership in manufacturing firms, Opoku, Choi, and Kang (2019) prove that the company can create innovative employees to search for new working techniques and to support and implement creative ideas in their workplace. In their study, Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020) demonstrate a positive association between servant leadership and innovative capability. Besides, Iqbal et al. (2020) affirm this evidence when researching employees working in an information technology company in Pakistan. Also, Bou Reslan et al. (2021) demonstrate that by applying servant leadership in the information and communication technology

companies in Latvia, the innovative working of employees becomes increases. By denoting this evidence, this study offers the second hypothesis as follows.

H₂: Servant leadership positively affects innovativeness.

2.3. Innovativeness and servant performance

Saunila (2017) uses the innovative capability aspects covering seven dimensions: (1) external knowledge, (2) work climate and well-being, (3) creativity and organizing structures, (4) regeneration, (5) participatory leadership culture, (6) individual activity, and (7) know-how development. Furthermore, she relates them with performance based on the perception of managers and employees in Finnish small and medium firms. Based on the managers' perspective, the performance is affected by dimensions three positively and five negatively. By mentioning the employees' viewpoints, the achievement is only positively influenced by the seventh. Furthermore, in their study, Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020) demonstrate that innovative capability is positively associated with performance. By denoting this evidence, this study offers the third hypothesis as follows.

H₃: Innovativeness positively affects servant performance

2.4. Research Model

By denoting three hypotheses formulated previously, the research model can be seen in the first diagram:

Diagram 1: Research Model

Source: Hypothesis Developed

3. Research Method

3.1. Variable Definition

Servant leadership (SL) acts as an exogenous variable in this study. Meanwhile, innovative capability (IC) and servant performance (SP) are endogenous. Mentioning Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020), SL is modeled as the first-order construct covering ten items (see Table 1).

Table 1: Servant leadership and its items

Indicator	Source
SL1: My leader executes his preaching.	Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020)
SL2: My leader serves the people without seeing race, gender, religion, etc.	
SL3: My leader perceives that his service is the responsibility of the others	
SL4: My leader acts humanly to everyone.	
SL5: My leader always prioritizes serving.	
SL6: My leader surrenders his life to assist everyone.	
SL7: My leader teaches me to have self-assurance rather than fear.	
S8: My leader is honest.	
S9: My leader contributes his work to society.	
S10: My leader encourages values exceeding his self-interest and successful substances.	

Additionally, innovativeness (INN) is modeled as the second-order construct by mentioning and modifying the items of Ruvio et al. (2014) in five dimensions: openness, future orientation, risk-taking, and proactiveness. Furthermore, each item of these dimensions is available in Table 2.

Table 2: The innovativeness: Its dimensions and their items

Dimension	Indicator	Source
Creativity	My leader stimulates me to be creative (C1). My leader can solve the problem creatively (C2). My leader requests that I develop service in the ministry (C3). My leader respects my creativity (C4). My leader encourages me to use a Holy Bible-based approach to handle the problems (C5).	Ruvio et al. (2014)
Openness	My church allows me to give my opinion (O1). My church allows me to create and develop ideas (O2). My church is positively open to change (O3). My leader constantly searches for new ways to solve problems (O4).	
Future orientation	My church sets clear goals (FO1). My leader ensures that the servants have the same vision (FO2). My leader communicates the future direction to the follower (FO3). My leader has a realistic vision for each ministry (FO4).	
Risk-taking	The riskier the action, the higher the benefit (RT1) My church applies an innovative strategy to take risks (RT2). My church prefers ministry with risk (RT3). My church does not like to play it safe (RT4)	
Proactiveness	My leader searches for opportunities for ministry development (P1). My leader initiatively shapes the environment for the result (P2). My leader always modified the function of ministry for the congregation (P3). My leader imitatively introduces a new administrative method to serve the congregation (P4).	

Furthermore, servant performance (SP) acts as the dependent variable. Again, to measure it, this research utilizes the idea of Otniel and Ardi (2022) based on the Christian values: spiritual gifts, heart, abilities, personality, dan experience (Warren, 2002). Based on them, this study proposes the items to measure servant performance:

1. The servant can develop and utilize my talents from God to serve the congregations (SP1).
2. The servant assists the community with all of my heart (SP2).
3. The servant utilizes the capability to help God through assemblies (SP3).
4. The servant uses the Christ-based temperament to serve God through communities well (SP4).
5. The servant shares the experiences with God to strengthen the faith of the congregations (SP5).

3.2. Population and Samples

As the population, this study employs the servants from *Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud*, Bandung, where the size (N) is 284. The formula of Issac dan Michael in Sugiyono (2017) is utilized to calculate the number of representative samples (RS). Moreover, this formula adopts the chi-square at the 5% significance level, P and Q of 0.5, and d of 0.05 (see the first equation).

$$RS = \frac{\chi^2 \text{ statistic} \cdot N \cdot P \cdot Q}{d^2(N-1) + \chi^2 \text{ statistic}(0,5)(0,5)} = \frac{\chi^2 \text{ statistic} \cdot N \cdot (0,5)(0,5)}{0,05^2(N-1) + \chi^2 \text{ statistic}(0,5)(0,5)} \quad (1)$$

After this formula is utilized, we find $RS = \frac{3.841 \cdot (284) \cdot (0,5)(0,5)}{0,05^2(284-1) + 3,841(0,5)(0,5)} = \frac{272.74}{1.67} = 163.529 \approx 164$. Moreover, this study uses the simple random sampling method to take them.

3.3. Method for data collection

This research surveys the respondents as samples to get their responses to items. According to Hartono (2013), this survey involves questionnaire distribution utilizing a five-point Likert scale, between 1 and 5, to demonstrate agreement and disagreement, respectively. Based on a survey in October 2021, of 164 servants selected as the sample, only 90 persons joined. Therefore, the response rate is $90/164 \times 100\% = 71.43\%$.

3.4. Method for analyzing responses

Because the total number of respondents is below 100, i.e., 90, this study employs the structural equation model based on variance to analyze the obtained response, as Ghozali (2021) explains. Moreover, the intended model can be seen in the second and third equations.

$$INN = \gamma_1 SL + \zeta_1 \quad (3)$$

$$SP = \gamma_2 SL + \beta_1 INN + \zeta_2 \quad (4)$$

Next, we test the validity and reliability of the collected responses. The answer to items or all items in each dimension is accurate if the loading factor is higher than 0.7 (Ghozali, 2017) and reliable if the Cronbach Alpha for them is above 0.7 (Ghozali, 2018).

Then, this model needs assessment by analyzing the contribution of all dependent variables (R-square), effect size (f-square), and predictive relevance (Q-square) (Ghozali, 2021).

- The cut-off value of the R-square for low, middle, and high contributions is 0.19, 0.33, and 0.67.
- The cut-off value of the f-square for weak, middle, and strong influence is 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35.
- If the Q-square is higher than 0, the model has predictive relevance.

Finally, to examine the proposed hypotheses, we compare the probability of the t-statistic with a 5% significance level for γ and β . The research hypotheses are acceptable if this value is lower than 5%.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. The organizational structure of Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud

Denoting the organizational structure of *Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud* (GKKD) in Bandung in the second diagram, the intended servants have a position under the elder board of three members. Under this board, the general secretary, assisted by office staff members and the treasurer, exists. In the line and staff organization, the deacon bureau performs as an adviser for the general secretary to formulate the policy in the church.

Under the general secretary, two shepherding departments exist. The first is for managing the established areas in Bandung; the second is for managing the development areas outside Bandung. Besides them, the youth department exists. Furthermore, apostolic, teaching, social service and congregation enablement, prophetic, and digital departments are available.

- The apostolic department has four divisions: (1) pionner, (2) maturation, (3) information and communication, and (4) area coordination of West Java.
- The teaching department has two divisions: (1) substance and curriculum and (2) training and equipment.
- The department of social service and congregation enablement department has two divisions. The first is related to the service to society, and the second is associated with the involvement of people in church activities.
- The prophetic department has six divisions: (1) praying, (2) worship leader, (3) choir and singer, (4) music, (5) dancer, and (6) assistance.
- The digital department has three divisions: (1) digital image, (2) content creator, and (3) technological information and media.

Diagram 2: Organizational Structure of *Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud* in Bandung
 Source: GKKD database

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

Of 164 servants chosen as the samples in *Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud*, only 90 persons give a complete response to the items. Furthermore, they are classified by demographic features, like age, gender, and last formal education, and church-related features, like position and duration to serve. The intended detail on the classification is obtainable in Table 3.

Table 3: The demographic and church-related features

Feature	Description	Total
Age	< 30 years old	2
	36 – 40 years old	12
	41 – 45 years old	23
	46 – 50 years old	21
	51 – 55 years old	23
	56 – 60 years old	7
	Above 60 years old	2
Gender	Man	52
	Woman	38
Last formal education	Senior high school	12
	Vocational school	11
	Bachelor	56
	Master	10
	Doctor	1

Table 3: The demographic and church-related features

Feature	Description	Total
Position in the church	Office administrative staff	1
	The head of shepherding and non-shepherding departments	9
	The pastors in shepherding departments	13
	Division coordinators in the non-shepherding departments	17
	Deacon Bureau	22
	Leader of the fellowship	19
Duration to serve in the church	From 0 to 5 years	6
	From 6 to 10 years	10
	From 11 to 15 years	5
	From 16 to 20 years	15
	From 21 to 25 years	20
	From 26 to 30 years	20
	From 31 to 35 years	11
	From 36 to 40 years	3

4.3. Instrumental Testing Result

At the starting step, this study finds some invalid items: SL10, O2, RT1, P1, and SP5 with loading factors below 0.5: 0.432, 0.467, -0.055, 0.428, 0.449. After that, this study removed them, and the result is shown in Table 4:

- The loading factor of SL1 until SL9 is more significant than 0.5: 0.641, 0.626, 0.519, 0.609, 0.675, 0.586, 0.501, 0.711, and 0.658. Therefore, the answers to these indicators are accurate.
- The loading factor of CR1 until CR4 is higher than 0.5: 0.804, 0.721, 0.808, and 0.766. Hence, the answers to these indicators are accurate. Similarly, the loading factor above 0.5 exists in O1, O3, and O4: 0.737, 0.847, and 0.879, FO1, FO2, FO3, and FO4: 0.639, 0.724, 0.710, and 0.763, RT2, RT3, and RT4: 0.845, 0.768, and 0.823, P2, P3, and P4: 0.591, 0.816, and 0.808. Also, the loading factor for LV_CR, LV_O, LV_FO, LV_RT, and LV_P is higher than 0.5: 0.800, 0.835, 0.870, 0.803, and 0.835. Thus, the dimensions meet the validity.
- The loading factor of SP1 until SP4 is upper than 0.5: 0.783, 0.503, 0.774, and 0.720. Therefore, the answers to these indicators are accurate.

Besides the validity result, Table 4 presents the reliability testing result reflected by its composite coefficient. In this table, the coefficients are above 0.7 for SL, CR, O, FO, RT, P, INN, and SP: 0.846, 0.858, 0.863, 0.802, 0.853, 0.787, 0.917, and 0.793. Based on this condition, the reliability test is already accomplished.

Table 4: Loading factor and composite reliability coefficient

Indicators/ Dimension	Loading factor							
	SL	CR	O	FO	RT	P	INN	SP
SL1	0.641							
SL2	0.626							
SL3	0.519							
SL4	0.609							
SL5	0.675							
SL6	0.586							
SL7	0.501							
SL8	0.711							
SL9	0.658							
CR1		0.804						
CR2		0.721						

Table 4: Loading factor and composite reliability coefficient

Indicators/ Dimension	Loading factor							
	SL	CR	O	FO	RT	P	INN	SP
CR3		0.808						
CR4		0.766						
O1			0.737					
O3			0.847					
O4			0.879					
FO1				0.639				
FO2				0.724				
FO3				0.710				
FO4				0.763				
RT2					0.845			
RT3					0.768			
RT4					0.823			
P2						0.591		
P3						0.816		
P4						0.808		
lv_CR							0.800	
lv_O							0.835	
lv_FO							0.870	
lv_RT							0.803	
lv_P							0.835	
SP1								0.783
SP2								0.503
SP3								0.774
SP4								0.720
Measurement	SL	CR	O	FO	RT	P	INN	SP
Composite Reliability	0.846	0.858	0.863	0.802	0.853	0.787	0.917	0.793

Source: The modified output of Warp PLS

4.4. The model assessment result

Table 5 shows the model assessment result based on R-squared, f-squared, and Q-squared. For the first model, the R-squared is 0.373: the contribution of servant leadership in explaining the variance of innovativeness is medium because this value is closely above 0.33. Furthermore, an f-squared of 0.373 shows a strong partial influence because of higher than the required level of 0.35. Meanwhile, the Q-squared of the first model is 0.371. Because this value is higher than 0, this model has the power to predict.

Table 5: The variance-based structural equation model estimation result

The related determinant	Model I: INN = f(SL)	Model II: SP = f(SL, INN)
	f-squared	f-squared
SL	0.373	0.182
INN	-	0.450
R-squared	0.373	0.633
Q-squared	0.371	0.630

Source: The modified output of Warp PLS

For the second model, the R-squared is 0.633, which means the contribution of servant leadership and innovativeness in explaining the variance of servant performance is almost strong because this value is next to 0.67. Furthermore, an f-squared of 0.182 for SL and 0.450 for INN. Because 0.182 is above 0.15 as the cut-off

value showing a medium influence, and 0.450 is upper than 0.350 as the cut-off value showing a substantial impact, servant leadership and innovativeness have partial medium and powerful effects, respectively.

4.5. The estimation model result

Table 6 presents the estimation result of the variance-based structural equation model consisting of the probability of the t-statistic. In the first model, this value is <0.001 for servant leadership. Because this value is lower than the 5-significance level, the second hypothesis is not rejected: servant leadership positively affects innovativeness. In the second model, this value is 0.002 for SL and <0.001 for INN. These values are still below the 5-significance level; consequently, the first and third hypotheses are acceptable.

Table 6: The variance-based structural equation model estimation result

Related determinants	Model I: INN = f(SL)		Model II: SP = f(SL, INN)	
	Coefficient	Probability of t-statistic	Coefficient	Probability of t-statistic
SL	0.611	<0.001	0.285	0.002
INN	-	-	0.591	<0.001

Source: The modified output of Warp PLS

4.6. Discussion

The first, second, and third hypotheses are accepted by mentioning the result of hypothesis testing in the earlier section. Receiving the first hypothesis proves a positive effect of servant leadership positively on performance. As the top leaders in the church, their actions have to be an example for the congregation serving as the servant, especially doing what their preach, realistically helping the unknown people and the assemblies without viewing their background, and conducting the service in ministry responsibly. They need to focus on assisting society in trouble and improving the self-confidence of the servants. These actions will be followed by servants to elevate their performance. Although having a different context, the positive impact of servant leadership on performance in this study confirms Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020), Tripathi et al. (2021), Sarwar et al. (2022), and Saleem et al. (2020).

Receiving the second hypothesis validates the positive influence of servant leadership on innovativeness. To make the ministry successful, the top leaders in the church should give their servants a chance to be creative in solving problems and developing ministry based on biblical concepts. Also, they need to allow the servants to provide constructive ideas. Importantly, leaders have to unite the visions and missions of the church by socializing them with the congregation through a meeting. Furthermore, the leaders must derive objectives and goals from the mission to support this situation. Based on the objectives, they formulate strategy and policy. To implement strategy, they must make programs and their budget and procedure. Besides, the leaders must take risks by faith, especially to share Gospel with the unbelievers through innovative techniques, such as utilizing YouTube channels. Furthermore, leaders must be proactive in developing the ministry by adding the functional scope. Even though having a different context, the positive impact of servant leadership on innovativeness in this study confirms Opoku et al. (2019), Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020), Iqbal et al. (2020), Bou Reslan et al. (2021).

Acknowledging the third hypothesis demonstrates a positive tendency of innovativeness on servant performance. This situation indicates the innovativeness of the church will effectively support the servants to work with their talents to glorify God. Despite having an unlike context, this positive tendency is in line with Saunila (2017) and Hernández-Perlines and Andrés Araya-Castillo (2020).

5. Conclusion

This study aims to enrich the Christian theological manuscripts designed quantitatively in the church context. The quantitative aspect can be seen through three hypotheses formulated: (1) a positive relationship between servant leadership and performance, (2) a positive association between servant leadership and innovativeness, and (3) a positive relationship between innovativeness and servant performance. Furthermore, to support this intention, this study uses the servants in *Gereja Kristen Kemah Daud*, Bandung to be respondents as the population and sample through the survey. This study reveals that three positive associations exist by denoting the response testing by structural equation model based on partial least square.

As the frontier, this research only utilizes two determinants of servant performance: servant leadership and innovativeness. This circumstance allows the subsequent researchers to add other factors affecting this performance, like organizational citizenship behavior and culture. Besides, they can treat innovativeness as the antecedent of the congregation's commitment. Testing these relationships together in one model can enrich the related findings.

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